

FACEBOOK: A SOCIAL NETWORK OR A WEAPON OF MISINFORMATION

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Abstract

Purpose – the purpose of this paper is to present and analyze whether, over the years, with the evolution of social networks and, in particular, "Facebook", they have become a weapon of manipulation and control of people around the world.

Methodology/approach – the article presents current and future trends from Facebook, and the content is based on secondary data.

Findings – in 2019, 70 countries use disinformation campaigns and according to a study, consisting of 56 countries, the number 1 platform in disinformation is represented by "Facebook".

Research limitations/implications – research has been quite elaborate in the care used or a wide range of resources

Practical implications – One of the main objectives of this article is to show how much people's lives are influenced by social networks and especially "Facebook".

Originality/value – The article is 100 percent original and represents 3 months of effective study

Key words: Social Media, digitization, influenced

Introduction

In the first case, we will start with the definition of digital marketing, followed by its classification, as well as the communication power of Social Media and especially "Facebook".

We have arrived in 2020 to be influenced by almost everything that is distributed on social networks and we consider that it is not the right direction, decisions that can sometimes work to our detriment. Sometimes, government agencies or well-meaning companies use this in presidential campaigns or in spreading the truth.

We will show what were the main factors that led to an increase in the power of social networks. Moreover, we will make a balanced analysis of the technologies that led to the development of digital marketing, which also includes social media, and also how "Facebook" has evolved over the years. We analyze the history of the most powerful social network and what were the steps to have over 2 billion users today.

Going further in our research, we will see more specific cases in which social media has really been a weapon of misinformation.

We will talk about "Cambridge Analytica" and the tools used by pro-Kremlin propaganda in favor of the ruling regime. We expect to reach some obvious results and to prove that social networks are really a weapon of misinformation.

At the moment, presidents are being elected with the help of social media, just as governments and regimes are being overthrown. In the beginning, Facebook was just a platform where you could see the pictures of colleagues from your university, today it has become one of the largest holders of personal information in the world but also a successful business model.

Chapter 1. Steps that have turned digital marketing into a tool for mass communication

1.1. Digital marketing – definition

Further researching the literature, we find in an article by Andreea Kuhn (2017), another definition of digital marketing, which tells us that digital marketing is a sub-branch of marketing, which aims to promote the products or services of a company with the help of the online environment. While some analysts say that digital marketing is any form of promotion that exists in the online environment (Peprimapagina, 2019), others say that digital marketing is mainly based on the Internet and has the role of using technology to promote a product, services, an organization as a whole, to create communities (Kondiment, 2018) or that it is a practice to promote services and products through the use of digital distribution channels, to reach the end consumer as quickly as possible, in a relevant, personal way, efficient and at the same time obtaining quantifiable results. (Syscomdigital, 2019)

Digicat (2019), a site about technology, reports that digital marketing represents, "the use of electronic technological means to communicate with targeted consumers and receive answers through the same communication channel."

1.2. Digital marketing classification

One of the greatest contemporary marketers (NeilPatel.com, 2019) makes a classification of digital marketing and tells us that it falls into two categories:

- online digital marketing
- digital offline marketing

Online marketing is divided into 9 distinct categories, as well as offline.

In the table below we will make a classification of digital marketing (table 1):

Table 1. Digital marketing classification

Online marketing	Offline marketing
Search engine optimization	Electronic panels
Search engine marketing	Digital product demos
Content marketing	Radio marketing
Social Media Marketing	TV commercials
Paid advertising per click	Telemarketing
Online public relations	Sponsored shows
Affiliate marketing	QR codes
Email marketing	Gifts, coupons,
E-Commerce	Programs loyalty

Source: the author based on the theory

Social media is a part of online digital marketing and today it is allocated a large part of marketing budgets.

Chapter 2. Social Media and its rise

2.1. What is Social Media?

Social Media is a mode of communication that advanced in the digital age with the development of the Internet but has a history in 1844 when the first message was transmitted using the "Morse" code. The message was "What has God wrought" and was broadcast between Baltimore and Washington

Social Media is a tool used to create online communities to share ideas, beliefs, written messages, and videos. (Historycooperative.org, 2015) A predecessor of Social Media that will come, having the same

principles of connectivity is the first email sent by Ray Tomlinson in 1971 between 2 computers connected in Cambridge, Massachusetts.

Another forerunner of today's Social Media is "Listserv", invented by Eric Thomas in 1986 and software which was the first automatic mailing list management application. (Interestingengineering.com, 2018)

2.2. The rise and development of social networks

With the growth and development of the Internet, the circumstances of development and social networks have emerged. If we talk about the evolution of Social Media and how it evolved in such a short time, we can not skip the first social network that appeared on the market, namely "Sixdegrees".

"Sixdegrees" was launched in 1997, it is the first site, the first Social Media network, which allows you to register with the email address through which you can later gather friends in your personal network, which has a significant volume of 3.5 million users and in 1999 it was bought for \$ 125 billion by the "YouthStream Media Networks" and in 2001 it was shut down.

Another cornerstone of the evolution of social networks is the appearance on the market of the "AmIHotOrNot.com" site, a site where users showed their appreciation for some photos uploaded to the platform. Moreover, in 2002, "Friendster" appeared, the first social network that allowed comments and by the end of the year it will reach up to 3 million users. "Myspace" is launched in 2003, one of the largest social sites, it will reach up to 25 million users and in 2005 the decline begins after it was acquired by "NewsCorp". Also in 2003, it appears on the page "Facemash", in response to "Hot or Not" by Mark Zuckerberg, and in 2004 it comes on the page with the social network "The Facebook" which will be transformed in 2005 into the well-known "Facebook". "The Facebook.com" domain costs \$ 200,000. (Samur, 2018)

In 2005, YouTube and Reddit appear on the market, and in the following years they appear on the "Twitter" market, "YouTube" is bought by "Google", "Facebook Ads" makes its debut together with the #Hashtag from "Twitter". Also, "Instagram" and "Pinterest" started in the social media market in 2010. In 2011 he launched "Snapchat", a social network very well known for the multitude of animated filters, followed in 2016 by "TikTok", a creative platform, initially dedicated to teenagers and which in 2016 reached 500 million users. (madart.land, 2020). In 2018, 3 billion inhabitants were accessing the internet, 2.1 of the planet's inhabitants have an open social media account of which 1.7 billion are active. (zenesys.com, 2019). And finally, to show once again the commercial power of social platforms, according to Statista, (2017), in the United States, on a sample aged 19-38 years, 48 percent bought products on social media, without having this intention at first. (Kumar, Nanda, 2019).

In figure 1 we have the main actors in social media.

Figure 1: Stages of Social Media accession
Source: The author based on the theory

2.3. “Facebook” – the most powerful social platform in the world

“Facebook” is a social networking site where people who have an active account can socialize, share opinions, and exchange wrote messages, voice messages, photos, and videos.

“Facebook” was founded by Mark Zuckerberg and several colleagues when he was still a student at “Harvard University”. Initially, the site was accessible only in the closed regime, only to “Harvard” students, later becoming accessible to all, who is over 13 years old. In June 2010, “Facebook” reached 500 million users’ “Facebook” accounts, and in the same year, “Google” announced that “Facebook” had become the most visited site in the world. On “Facebook”, users can create a personal profile, add other users to the personal network, join various virtual groups but can also appreciate some pages of personal interest, this being possible in 2009 when the “like” button appeared. To give an example of the strength of “Facebook”, we will mention the campaign launched by the company “Nike” in the “Football World Cup” in 2010 when after the addition of an advertisement by marketers, it was seen by 8 million fans in just a few minutes. (Edosomwan et al., 2011)

Chapter 3. Social media campaigns that have led to changes in perception for personal purposes

3.1. Cambridge Analytica

The story of Cambridge Analytica consists of the access of 85 million “Facebook” users with the help of a “Facebook” partner application, “Thisisyourdigitallife”,(Mediafax, 2019) created in the Republic of Moldova, which offered access to the preferences and characteristics of users, those from Cambridge Analytica having this data, and was able to send personalized political messages. Cambridge Analytica worked for Donald Trump in the 2016 presidential campaign but also used user data in the Brexit campaign in the United Kingdom (UK) and to leave the European Union. “Facebook” has been fined £ 500,000 for failing to comply with personal data protection. (cursdeguvernare.ro, 2019)

3.2. Pro-Kremlin propaganda and massive misinformation using “Facebook”

When we talk about misinformation, we can't help but talk about the "troll armies" used by the Kremlin administration to turn certain unfavorable situations to their advantage. They use certain principles of misinformation: “How do you get rid of an enemy? You create another enemy for him! “.

"Troll armies" are nothing more than well-organized groups that use fake social media accounts, but generally “Facebook”, which repeats a message endlessly with the help of social platforms and that news, the action ends up being believed by “Facebook” users. They use several tools to spread "false news", "Russia Today" (in English, Russian, German), "RIA Novosti" and "Sputnik" (in English).

“Facebook” tells us that there are about 270 million fake accounts, it is very easy to imagine if these accounts start to focus on a cause that is often not true and start to misinform or attack a person, presidential candidate, government, social minority. We cannot forget the pro-Kremlin actions when they broadcast news that the crisis in Ukraine and the 2014 “Maidan” disaster were started by Georgian snipers, who were paid \$ 20 a day. Or that the Central Information Administration (CIA) promotes gay parades in Russia. Moreover, we cannot forget the tragic event that took place on June 17, 2014, when the “MH17” plane was shot down, and Russia's misinformation showed that those in an area controlled by Ukraine were guilty. According to "BuzzSumo" between 2018-2019 were published on social networks no more than "12759" articles on this topic. (mediastandard.ro, 2019)

Discussion and conclusions

Following this research, we reached several conclusions as follows: First of all, we must make huge campaigns against false news, the public must be informed and educated, and at the same time, we believe that not all black ambulances came to steal our children and "Soros" is not the universal evil. Users should be encouraged to stop accessing news that they consider doubtful, to stop accessing sites that they do not trust, and that have appeared "like mushrooms after rain." In addition, the most commonly used misinformation directions are political opponents, the attack on human rights, but also misinformation campaigns of political dissidents.

In 2019, 70 countries use disinformation campaigns and according to a study, consisting of 56 countries, the number 1 platform in disinformation is represented by "Facebook". (Bradshaw, Howard, 2019)

What was wanted to be a model to connect more easily has become a weapon of influence and hatred between peers. Technology companies are the richest in the world because they have an invaluable commodity, namely data about their users, data that today have come to be worth more than crude oil.

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